

**METHODS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE
COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF THE TOURISM DIRECTION IN
ENGLISH CLASSES**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the formation and development of the dynamics of communicative and organizational abilities of students studying in the direction of tourism in a regional context. Students studying in the direction of pedagogical and technical education are studied in the educational process of the communicative features. Tourism of the educational process the dependence of the formation and development of the dynamics of communicative and organizational skills and communication of students on professional motivation is analyzed and studied in an expressive way. There will also be feedback and feedback on the use of modern Information Technology in the development of communicative competence of students of the tourism direction.

Keywords: linguistic knowledge, communication, communicative skills, tourism, students, communicative competence, information technology.

Communicative competence usually refers to the ability to establish and maintain the necessary contacts with other people. Competence includes a set of knowledge, skills and competencies that provide effective communication. This type of competence includes the ability to change the depth and scope of communication, to understand and be understood by communication partners. Communicative competence is the experience of developing and mainly conscious communication between people, which is formed in the context of

direct interaction. The process of improving communicative competence is associated with the development of the individual. The means of regulating communicative actions are part of human culture, and their assimilation and enrichment occurs in accordance with the same laws as the development and reproduction of the entire cultural heritage. In many ways, the acquisition of communicative experience occurs not only in the process of direct interaction. A person also receives information from literature, theater, cinema about the essence of communicative situations, about the problems of interpersonal interaction and how to solve them. In the process of mastering the communicative sphere, a person receives tools from the cultural environment to analyze communicative situations in verbal and visual forms.

Today, the education of young people with independent thinking, creative activities remains one of the main tasks. Because it is clear and clear that education gives creativity to youth spirituality, that all the aspirations of the growing young generation come true through modern education. Increasing the communicative abilities of students studying especially in the direction of Tourism, their ability to communicate correctly, serves for tourists to easily understand them and the development of the tourism industry as well. The study of the formation of communication skills and the development of communicative abilities and the formation of motivation in the educational process of education is one of the factors that determine the effectiveness of Education.

Innovative educational technology is a methodology for organizing educational activities, which includes some new or qualitative improvement of existing methods and tools to improve the effectiveness of the educational process in the field of Tourism and create conditions for educational activities that best suit the current trends in socio-economic development. of society. Innovations also develop in the process of educational activities. In the educational process, the direction of tourism is carried out to develop theoretical

and practical knowledge of students, which can then be applied in various areas of practical life associated with the creation of innovations.

One of the tools for the development of communicative competence of students of the tourism direction is social and psychological training (SPT). This relatively new scientific and practical direction of psychology is currently receiving intensive development as an integral and important part of the psychological service system. With the variety of specific forms of SPT, they all have a unifying property - a means of influence aimed at the development of certain knowledge, skills and experiences in the field of interpersonal communication. It can be said that psychologically it means the following:

- development of skills and communication skills system;
- correction of the existing interpersonal communication system;
- creating personal conditions for successful communication.

In the context of pedagogical education, the dynamic increase in communicative and organizational skills and levels of communication in students as they move from course to course was determined during the studies. As students move to a higher course, responding to seminar classes, organizing lectures on the basis of new pedagogical technologies, which creates opportunities, conditions for each student to develop their communicative skills, such as stating their independent opinion, protecting their own opinion. At the same time, the passage of the subject "training methodology" in fourth-year students also plays a factor in the high level of development of communicative abilities in them. Also, pedagogical practice, which is carried out in the 4th courses, contributes significantly to their formation as a specialist and the high level of development of their communicative abilities.

We have witnessed a dynamic increase in the level of self-government in communication as students studying tourism move from course to course. While communicative control is shown to be weak in L-course students, it is clear that communicative control is at a high level in graduate courses. And in students with

technical education, it is not difficult to notice that the indicator of communicative control has changed from a sluggish level in lower courses to a medium level in graduate courses. Therefore, in the conditions of pedagogical education, students were observed to increase neither only communicative and organizational skills, but also the level of self-control in communication.

Due to the social nature of the tourism industry and therefore the need for linguistic individuals, the study of individual communicative activities, the language and speech behavior of people, especially in their professional work, is relevant and timely. To communicate correctly, it is necessary to have a sufficient amount of systematized knowledge about history, culture, human consciousness and behavior, forms of social development, as well as access to verbal and non-verbal means of communication. Thus, it is very important that you have a developed communicative competence, which is a system of knowledge and skills necessary for effective communication.

It is they who, in the end, the method and direction of communication, on the other hand, the low level of professional communicative competence of students of the tourism direction does not allow him to realize himself as a professional, as a result of which, in general, can cause dissatisfaction with life. Taking into account the interaction of this general and professional communicative competence, we identified the following criteria for its manifestation: the first criterion is general communicative values. We have included in them the value of a person for the process of work, the value of the process of communication, the value of traditional forms of communication; the second criterion – their implementation of interpersonal communication should be defined as general communicative skills.

The role of motivation in the formation of professional skills and qualifications in the personality of students. Because there is an internal force that directs a person's activity, which gives specific directions and instructions to the content of the work being done. Especially for students of the tourism direction,

being able to make successful communication is one of the most important tasks. The reason is that they work directly with tourists, and it is necessary that they treat not only foreign tourists, but also domestic tourists. This also has a positive effect on later visits by even more tourists to our country.

Innovative technologies in education are used on the basis of the application of certain approaches to teaching, i.e. principles are set, including the requirements and goals that are the basis for the development of new technologies. Therefore, the highest goal is to increase the quality of education by constantly developing the activities of innovative technologists in education, which are used and should be applied in the educational process, using them more widely.

For example, in order to increase the communicative abilities of students of the tourism direction, such technologies are based on a complex of techniques and tools that involve the use of traditional and innovative technologies: independent work with educational literature, the use of audiovisual, multimedia tools, differentiated teaching methods. Innovations in education - everything related to the introduction into practice of advanced pedagogical experience. The educational process, which occupies a leading place in modern science, is aimed at giving students knowledge, skills, skills, the formation of personality, civic qualities. Changes are determined by changes in time, education, education, attitude to development. The goal of communicative self-improvement is clear, but motives can vary. For a humanely oriented teacher, communicative self-improvement should be accompanied not only in self-improvement for oneself, but also as a basic condition for the implementation of an effective interaction, which contributes to the development of children, their individuality and originality.

For a tourism professional, professional communication skills and personal qualities such as friendship and willpower are very important, since the field of tourism is mainly the field of human interaction and communication. Thus, the

system of communicative skills of a tourism specialist consists of: establishing communication in the communication process, being flexible, polite and emotionally stable, knowing verbal and non-verbal means of communication, having a sense of humor, knowing language etiquette, arguing one point of view, etc.

There are a number of communicative requirements for tourism industry and hospitality workers. These are: communication, the desire to work with people, kindness, compassion, tolerance, the ability to analyze the surrounding and their own behavior, the ability to understand their intentions and relationships, the ability to understand people's relationships, the ability to overcome their differences and organize their interaction, the ability to empathize, to find a common language with different individuals, accuracy, self-education, knowledge of human psychology, etc. Researchers of professional communication issues in the field of Tourism distinguish certain characteristics and personal qualities that make up the behavior of employees, characterized by a high level of operational readiness for effective professional communication. Such an employee:

- tends to actively discuss and resolve issues that arise;
- aimed at achieving the best results in professional communication;
- has professional and communicative competence, can find optimal solutions;
- aware of the impact of cultural differences on the results of professional and business relations;
- has a polite, positive attitude and an optimistic worldview.

Non-verbal means-facial expressions, posture, gestures, gaze, pantomime-are often much brighter than oral speech. They reflect mental, especially emotional, conditions that are usually spontaneous and not controlled by conscience, while verbal communication involves the use of linguistic signs inseparable from consciousness and awareness. Thus, nonverbal information is often nonverbal because it reflects the internal state of the individual.

In conclusion, in increasing the communicative competencies of students of the tourism direction, it is necessary that the use of Information Technology of various types is part of Education. In particular, knowledge of foreign languages is also one of the most important factors. In the process of mastering language, a person learns the basic forms and laws of thinking, which makes it possible to go beyond direct emotional images and reach the level of concepts. The study of foreign languages accelerates the mental development of the individual, increases his ideological culture. You also need to improve the language of non-verbal communication, which is not only the language of gestures, but also emotions. It is well known that the same word, such as greeting or thanking, can be spoken with different colors that are transmitted through facial expressions, gestures, tone and reflect the subtle nuances of human emotions and feelings. For non-verbal communication, it is customary to use non-verbal signs as the main means of transmitting information, forming an image, opinion about the interlocutor and influencing another person.

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